

Fibonacci-type Sequences and Roots of Unity

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Abstract

In this paper, we will present a new relationship linking the Fibonacci sequence to the square roots of unity represented by the set $\{\mp 1, \mp i\}$ and the cubic roots of unity represented by the set $\{\mp 1, \mp \omega, \mp \omega^2\}$. This relationship will form a complex iterative sequence that continues to infinity, from which a new sequence is generated, which we have named the $H_n Alqazzaz$ sequence. This sequence follows the same pattern as the Fibonacci sequence, using two initial terms, but with a different relationship. Its terms depend on the square and cubic roots of unity, which we have defined and specified its conditions. This sequence generates sequences that vary in their frequency depending on the initial terms.

Keywords: Fibonacci sequence, Fibonacci-type sequences, Lucas numbers, complex iterative sequence, roots of unity.

1 Preliminaries

In this section, we review the fundamental mathematical structures required for this study, including classical integer sequences and the algebraic properties of roots of unity in the complex plane.

1.1 The Fibonacci Sequence

The Fibonacci sequence $\{F_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ is a sequence of integers characterized by a constant linear recurrence relation. It is formally defined as:

$$F_n = F_{n-1} + F_{n-2}$$

with initial values $F_0 = 0$ and $F_1 = 1$. This sequence is a primary example of additive growth in number theory [1].

1.2 The Lucas Sequence

The Lucas sequence $\{L_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ follows the same recurrence relation as the Fibonacci sequence but is distinguished by different starting parameters:

$$L_n = L_{n-1} + L_{n-2}$$

with initial values $L_0 = 2$ and $L_1 = 1$. Lucas numbers are closely related to Fibonacci numbers through various algebraic identities and the golden ratio [2].

1.3 Square Roots of Unity

The square roots of unity are defined as the complex solutions to the polynomial equation $z^2 - 1 = 0$. This set consists of the elements $\{1, -1\}$. Geometrically, these points represent a symmetry of order 2 across the origin in the complex plane. [3]

1.4 Cube Roots of Unity

The cube roots of unity are the solutions to the equation $z^3 - 1 = 0$. These roots consist of the real number 1 and two complex conjugate numbers ω and ω^2 , given by: [4]

$$\omega = e^{2\pi i/3} = -\frac{1}{2} + i\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, \quad \omega^2 = e^{4\pi i/3} = -\frac{1}{2} - i\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

2 Fibonacci-type sequences and the imaginary unit

2.1 Fibonacci sequence repetition with i

In an attempt to relate the Fibonacci sequence with the complex numbers, each Fibonacci number was raised to the number i as follows:

$$i^0 = 1, i^1 = i, i^1 = i, i^2 = -1, i^3 = -i, i^5 = i$$

This is the first six terms in a sequence, and when we advance and calculate the rest of the terms in the same way, they will be as follows:

$$i^8 = 1, i^{13} = i, i^{21} = i, i^{34} = -1, i^{55} = -i, i^{89} = i$$

We will notice that there is a repetition in the outputs and that the first six terms in the sequence are equal to their values when raising the following six terms and that the seventh term when raised to the i is equal to the first term when it is raised to the i , as well as when continuing and calculating the rest of the terms of the sequence are as follows:

$$i^{144} = 1, i^{233} = i, i^{377} = i, i^{610} = -1, i^{987} = -i, i^{1597} = i$$

We notice that the results are equal at *mod* (6) for the terms and not for their values.

2.2 sequences like Fibonacci repetition with i

The Fibonacci sequence, which begins with the first term 0 and the second term 1, the similar sequences that work on the same principle but with the difference of the first term and the second term.

Like *Lucas numbers*, the first term which is 2 and the second term is 1. It is as follows: {2, 1, 3, 4, 7, 11, 18, 29, 47, 76, 123, 199, 322, 521, ...}

We will work in the same way as the Fibonacci setting when raised the Lucas numbers for i , it is as follows:

$$i^2 = -1, i^1 = i, i^3 = -i, i^4 = 1, i^7 = -i, i^{11} = -i$$

These are the first six terms in Lucas number, and when we advance and calculate the rest of the terms in the same way, they will be as follows:

$$i^{18} = -1, i^{29} = i, i^{47} = -i, i^{76} = 1, i^{123} = -i, i^{199} = -i$$

We will notice that there is a repetition in the results and that the first six terms in Lucas' numbers are equal to their values when raising the following six terms and that the seventh term when raising the power of is equal to the first term when raising the power of, as well as when continuing and calculating the rest of the terms:

$$i^{322} = -1, i^{521} = i, i^{843} = -i, i^{1364} = 1, i^{2207} = -i, i^{3571} = -i$$

We notice that the results are equal at *mod* (6) for the terms and not for their values.

2.3 Generalization of the Fibonacci pattern to the rest of the numbers

As mentioned above, the Fibonacci sequence is the addition of two terms to give the previous term, but what if random numbers are taken to be the first and second terms:

For example: the first term is 4589 and the second term is 6723, so it is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} i^{4589} = i, i^{6723} = -i, i^{11312} = 1, i^{18035} = -i, i^{29347} = -i, i^{47382} = -1 \\ i^{76729} = i, i^{124111} = -i, i^{200840} = 1, i^{324951} = -i, i^{525791} = -i, i^{850742} = -1 \end{aligned}$$

The frequency is also for every six terms, and the outcomes are equal at *mod* (6) for the terms and not for their values.

Hence, we may notice that the distinctive property of Fibonacci may not be related to the fact that the first term is 0 and the second term is 1, and vice versa, because when we take the first two terms as larger numbers, we notice that the sequence reaches the golden ratio faster than the Fibonacci sequence reaches it.

3 Generalization of Fibonacci-type sequences on roots of unity

3.1 Square roots of unity

3.1.1 Raising sequences for {1, -1}

When we raise the sequences to the 1 it will be a trivial case.

When we raised to -1, it will generate a repetition of every three terms.

This can be seen as follows:

1. with Fibonacci sequences

$$\begin{aligned} -1^0 = 1, \quad -1^1 = -1, \quad -1^2 = 1 \\ -1^3 = -1, \quad -1^4 = 1, \quad -1^5 = -1 \end{aligned}$$

2. with Lucas number

$$\begin{aligned} -1^2 = 1, \quad -1^3 = -1, \quad -1^4 = -1 \\ -1^5 = 1, \quad -1^6 = -1, \quad -1^7 = -1 \end{aligned}$$

3. with random number

$$\begin{aligned} -1^{4589} &= -1, & -1^{6723} &= -1, & -1^{11312} &= 1 \\ -1^{18035} &= -1, & -1^{29347} &= -1, & -1^{47382} &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

3.1.2 Raising sequences for i

When we raised to i , it will generate a repetition of every six terms.
This can be seen as follows:

1. with Fibonacci sequences

$$i^0 = 1, \quad i^1 = i, \quad i^2 = -1, \quad i^3 = -i, \quad i^4 = 1, \quad i^5 = i$$

2. with Lucas number

$$i^2 = -1, \quad i^3 = -i, \quad i^4 = 1, \quad i^5 = i, \quad i^6 = -1, \quad i^7 = -i, \quad i^8 = 1, \quad i^9 = i, \quad i^{10} = -1, \quad i^{11} = -i$$

3. with random number

$$\begin{aligned} i^{4589} &= i, & i^{6723} &= -i, & i^{11312} &= 1, \\ i^{18035} &= -i, & i^{29347} &= -i, & i^{47382} &= -1 \end{aligned}$$

3.1.3 Raising sequences for $-i$

When we raised to $-i$, it will generate a repetition of every six terms.
This can be seen as follows:

1. with Fibonacci sequences

$$-i^0 = 1, \quad -i^1 = -i, \quad -i^2 = -1, \quad -i^3 = i, \quad -i^4 = 1, \quad -i^5 = -i$$

2. with Lucas number

$$-i^2 = -1, \quad -i^3 = -i, \quad -i^4 = 1, \quad -i^5 = i, \quad -i^6 = 1, \quad -i^7 = i, \quad -i^8 = -1, \quad -i^9 = -i, \quad -i^{10} = -1, \quad -i^{11} = i$$

3. with random number

$$\begin{aligned} -i^{4589} &= -i, & -i^{6723} &= i, & -i^{11312} &= 1, \\ -i^{18035} &= i, & -i^{29347} &= i, & -i^{47382} &= -1 \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Cube roots of unity

3.2.1 Raising sequences for 1

When we raise the sequences to the 1 it will be a trivial case.

3.2.2 Raising sequences for ω

When we raised to ω , it will generate a repetition of every eight terms. This can be seen as follows:

1. with Fibonacci sequences

$$\begin{aligned}\omega^0 &= 1, & \omega^1 &= \omega, & \omega^2 &= \omega^2, \\ \omega^3 &= 1, & \omega^5 &= \omega^2, & \omega^8 &= \omega^2, & \omega^{13} &= \omega\end{aligned}$$

2. with Lucas number

$$\begin{aligned}\omega^2 &= \omega^2, & \omega^1 &= \omega, & \omega^3 &= 1, & \omega^4 &= \omega, \\ \omega^7 &= \omega, & \omega^{11} &= \omega^2, & \omega^{18} &= 1, & \omega^{29} &= \omega^2\end{aligned}$$

3. with random number

$$\begin{aligned}\omega^{4589} &= \omega^2, & \omega^{6723} &= 1, & \omega^{11312} &= \omega^2, & \omega^{18035} &= \omega^2, \\ \omega^{29347} &= \omega, & \omega^{47382} &= 1, & \omega^{76729} &= \omega, & \omega^{124111} &= \omega\end{aligned}$$

3.2.3 Raising sequences for ω^2

When we raised to ω^2 , it will generate a repetition of every eight terms. This can be seen as follows:

1. with Fibonacci sequences

$$\begin{aligned}\omega^{20} &= 1, & \omega^{21} &= \omega^2, & \omega^{21} &= \omega^2, & \omega^{22} &= \omega, \\ \omega^{23} &= 1, & \omega^{25} &= \omega, & \omega^{28} &= \omega, & \omega^{213} &= \omega^2\end{aligned}$$

2. with Lucas number

$$\begin{aligned}\omega^{22} &= \omega, & \omega^{21} &= \omega^2, & \omega^{23} &= 1, & \omega^{24} &= \omega^2, \\ \omega^{27} &= \omega^2, & \omega^{211} &= \omega, & \omega^{218} &= 1, & \omega^{229} &= \omega\end{aligned}$$

3. with random number

$$\begin{aligned}\omega^{24589} &= \omega, & \omega^{26723} &= 1, & \omega^{211312} &= \omega, & \omega^{218035} &= \omega, \\ \omega^{229347} &= \omega^2, & \omega^{247382} &= 1, & \omega^{276729} &= \omega^2, & \omega^{2124111} &= \omega^2\end{aligned}$$

4 H_n Alqazzaz sequences

4.1 Definition of the H_n Alqazzaz sequences

We have previously observed that the Fibonacci sequence and similar sequences, when their numbers are raised to square and cube roots, generate a recurring pattern, and that this pattern can be formed without referring to the Fibonacci sequence or any other similar sequence, but rather it can be generated through this new sequence which depends on two terms and according to the following formula:

$$H_n = H_{n-1} \times H_{n-2}, \text{ which is } H_{n-1}, H_{n-2} \in \{\mp 1, \mp i, \mp \omega, \mp \omega^2\}$$

The repetitions in this sequence vary according to the first two terms.

4.2 Examples

Example 1.

Consider the H_n Alqazzaz sequence with initial terms $H_0 = i$ and $H_1 = -1$. Write the first iteration.

Solution:

$$H_n = \{i, -1, -i, i, 1, i\}$$

Example 2.

Consider the H_n Alqazzaz sequence with initial terms $H_0 = i$ and $H_1 = \omega$. Write the first iteration.

Solution:

H_n	term	H_n	term	H_n	term
H_0	i	H_8	i	H_{16}	-1
H_1	ω	H_9	ωi	H_{17}	$-\omega i$
H_2	ωi	H_{10}	$-\omega$	H_{18}	ωi
H_3	$\omega^2 i$	H_{11}	$-\omega^2 i$	H_{19}	ω^2
H_4	-1	H_{12}	i	H_{20}	i
H_5	$-\omega^2 i$	H_{13}	ω^2	H_{21}	$\omega^2 i$
H_6	$\omega^2 i$	H_{14}	$\omega^2 i$	H_{22}	$-\omega^2$
H_7	ω	H_{15}	ωi	H_{23}	$-\omega i$

5 Conclusion

In this study, we made a unique connection between number theory, represented by the famous Fibonacci sequence, the complex numbers and the imaginary units in them, especially the square and cubic unity roots. This generated a new sequence that combines the two branches and has properties that make it of great importance in understanding complex patterns. In future work, we will publish research papers that take us to greater horizons in complex analysis.

References

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